

HISTORY OF RESEARCH ON PSYCHOPEDAGOGY CARRIED OUT IN STRICTU-SENSU POSTGRADUATE COURSES FINANCED BY CAPES

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10116593

Marcus Vinicius Peralva Santos

Educational Business Coordinator at Senac Araçatuba (SP). Doctor and master in Geology, with degrees in Pedagogy, Biology and Marketing. Specialist in Pedagogical Coordination and Management of Education and Training of New Managers.

Email: mperalva@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

Psychopedagogy is the science that studies the process of building knowledge (teaching-learning process), taking advantage of knowledge from the areas of Psychology and Pedagogy. Although it may seem like a recent term, for many people, their studies have already exceeded 30 years in Brazil. Based on this premise, the general objective of this article is to describe the historical evolution of work financed by CAPES in strictu-sensu postgraduate courses in Brazil, having carried out a bibliographical survey of such work on the Thesis Catalog website. and CAPES Dissertations, adopting the term “psychopedagogy” as the keyword in searches. It can be seen that the first funded works date back to the end of the 80s, and these were published almost uninterruptedly over the years, the only exception being the year 1994, where no publications financed by Capes on the subject were found. theme. The type of work that received the largest investments were academic master's dissertations (212), with the largest number of publications occurring in the years 1995, 2003, 2008 and 2016 (15 works for each year). Finally, among the various areas of activity in Psychopedagogy, there is clearly the area of Education, as the one with the largest production of content in this science.

Keywords : Psychopedagogy. Psychopedagogical clinic. Teaching-learning.

INTRODUCTION

Psychopedagogy is studied in different areas of knowledge, such as Education, Psychology, Arts, Teaching, among others. Its origin is interdisciplinary, having a knowledge base in Psychology and Pedagogy, but in short it seeks to understand the Teaching-learning process, so that any individual has the basic conditions to acquire any form of knowledge they want to seek (MAIA and RICHETTI, 2022).

In the literature there is no consensus on what the correct origin of Psychopedagogy would be. It is believed that its origins occurred in the 20th century, in Europe, with the world's first Psychopedagogy Center appearing in the 1920s. Other researchers link its emergence to 1946, when the first Psychopedagogical Centers in Europe were created. (MOURA et al., 2019).

The professional psychopedagogue, once he comes to practice the profession, is able to recognize the elements that allow the individual to practice learning, so that his challenge, whether working in a clinic or in an institutional environment, will be to contribute so that this individual can develop more and more, in particular, in those cases where there is some type of learning difficulty (BOSSA, 2016).

The general objective of this article is to describe the historical evolution of work financed by CAPES in strictu-sensu postgraduate courses in Brazil, whose theme addresses the theme of Psychopedagogy. In order to achieve the general objective presented here, the following are specific objectives: (a) List the main studies regarding their themes over the years; (b) classify them according to their type; and (c) classify them according to their area of knowledge.

The methodology used in this research consisted of carrying out a bibliographical survey of authors who reflect on the topic of Psychopedagogy, seeking to acquire information and explanations to resolve the doubts that arose regarding the areas of activity of the psychopedagogue and their funding from CAPES.

This research is justified, therefore, the perspective of Psychopedagogy's performance is of great importance for the educational scenario, since educational practices linked to this theme can be applied to various aspects of activity, including both music (OLIVEIRA, 1991; FIGUEIREDO, 1996; GIL, 1997; BASTOS, 1999), errors in learning (LAJONQUIERE, 1992), Youth and Adult Education (EJA) (PEDROSO, 2010), entrepreneurship and multiple intelligences (MATIAS, 2010), school failure (MENEZES, 2011), among others.

METHODOLOGY

This article is descriptive in nature, in which a bibliographical research was carried out using the database of the CAPES Theses and Dissertations Catalog website (<https://catalogodeteses.capes.gov.br/catalogo-teses/#!/>), in which we searched for works that presented the theme “Psychopedagogy” in their context.

As guiding items, for the selection of these works, it was decided to select all the works that presented the term “Psychopedagogy” incorporated in their title or in the body of the text,

carrying out a prior reading of it, in order to verify if it really was aligned with the theme of the present study. There was no temporal restriction regarding the year of publication.

As for its approach, it is qualitative-quantitative, having as premises the analysis of the quantity of works financed year by year and the descriptive (qualitative) analysis of the forms of application of Psychopedagogy in its various aspects of activity.

The data obtained was converted into graphs and charts, which were generated using the Microsoft Office Word 2016 program.

HISTORY OF STUDIES FINANCED ON PSYCHOPEDAGOGY BY CAPES

In order to better elucidate the information contained in this article, the data presented here are organized into two subtopics, namely: (1) “CAPES”, which describes its functionality and relationship with postgraduate courses -graduation from Brazil, and (2) “List of studies in Psychopedagogy financed by CAPES” which aims to present the work financed and defended with CAPES from 1980 to 2022, in addition to discussing other pertinent aspects.

Capes

The Foundation for the Coordination of Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES) of the Ministry of Education corresponds to a development agency that provides, through periodic notices, scholarships and grants for scientific research to people interested in obtaining them, as long as they meet the requirements. basic requirements for obtaining it, such as being linked to a higher education institution (RIBEIRO, 2017).

Until 2017, CAPES accounted for 55% of the scholarships granted to postgraduate students in the country, differentiating itself from other funding agencies in the country, such as CNPq and State Foundations for Research Support, as it is also a research body. assessment of the quality of *stricto-sensu* postgraduate courses (Masters and Doctorate) (RIBEIRO, 2017).

According to data made available in April 2023 on the Sucupira Platform website (<https://sucupira.capes.gov.br/>), the Southeast region is the one with the largest number of postgraduate programs in the country, a total of 1979, as well as the largest number of postgraduate courses, a total of 3171, while the northern region has the lowest number of programs and courses (Tables 1 and 2) (BRASIL, 2023a).

In addition to investing in research, CAPES provides the entire national and international community with a website specialized in publishing articles, e-books, among other

scientific materials. This is the CAPES Periodicals Portal, which can be accessed through the link: <https://www-periodicos-capes-gov-br.ez1.periodicos.capes.gov.br/>

Table 01 – Number of postgraduate programs linked to the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel in April 2023

Region	Total Postgraduate Programs						
	Total	ME	OF	MP	DP	FEAR	MP/DP
MIDWEST	397	147	7	64	1	176	two
NORTH EAST	960	384	16	162	1	387	10
NORTH	289	131	7	54	0	91	6
SOUTHEAST	1979	370	36	374	1	1175	23
SOUTH	974	278	11	145	0	526	14
Totals	4599	1310	77	799	3	2355	55

Note: ME: Academic Master's degree; DO: Academic Doctorate; MP: Professional Master's Degree; DP: Professional Doctorate; ME/DO: Academic Masters and Academic Doctorate; MP/DP: Professional Master's and Professional Doctorate.

Source: BRAZIL, 2023b

Table 02 – Number of postgraduate courses linked to the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel in April 2023

Region	Total Postgraduate Courses				
	Total	ME	OF	MP	DP
MIDWEST	575	323	183	66	3
NORTH EAST	1356	770	403	172	11
NORTH	378	216	96	60	6
SOUTHEAST	3171	1541	1210	396	24
SOUTH	1505	799	534	158	14
Totals	6985	3649	2426	852	58

Note: ME: Academic Master's degree; DO: Academic Doctorate; MP: Professional Master's Degree; DP: Professional Doctorate; ME/DO: Academic Masters and Academic Doctorate; MP/DP: Professional Master's and Professional Doctorate.

Source: BRAZIL, 2023b

List of Studies in Psychopedagogy Funded by Capes

Given this scenario of numerous aspects of psychopedagogy in education, this study seeks to evaluate the investments made by CAPES in conjunction with research focused on this topic. According to the analyzes carried out in the CAPES Catalog of Theses and Dissertations (<https://catalogodeteses.capes.gov.br/catalogo-teses/#!/>) it can be seen that the number of works defended over the years showed large fluctuations, as can be seen in Table 3.

The first works defended on Psychopedagogy, which were financed by CAPES, here in Brazil, took place in 1989, three in total (Table 3). Two are classified as belonging to the area of knowledge of Education, namely “Psychopedagogical Clinic – bases for a methodology”

authored by Vania Guedes Nin Ferreira and “In search of a theoretical foundation for psychopedagogy” authored by Maria Cecília GV Almeida E Silva. The third work falls within the area of Nursing knowledge, “From professional metalanguage to the development of scientific technical vocabulary in the area of Nursing” written by Noemia Simões. For this specific year, the works defended were of the academic master's type, and they were not available on the Sucupira platform for download.

In the period from 1990 to 1992, the number of publications fluctuated up and down, depending on the year, with 1, 3 and 2 dissertations being defended, respectively, each year, five in the Education area and 1 in the Nursing area. , and as with the 1989 works, these works are also not available for consultation on the Sucupira platform (Table 3). A novelty occurred in 1992, the work entitled “From Piaget to Freud: notes to rethink errors in learning. (Psycho) Pedagogy between knowledge and knowledge” written by Leandro de Lajonquiere was the first thesis defended in the country financed by CAPES.

In 1993, a peak in master's degree defenses occurred for the first time, timidly. In total, six works had their results presented, all in the area of Education, corresponding to twice the number of defenses carried out in the previous years that had had the biggest peaks, in this case 1991 and 1989, both with three defenses. However, in 1994, for the first and only time, until then, there was no defense of work financed by CAPES in the area of Psychopedagogy (Table 3).

The years 1995, 2003, 2008 and 2016 are characterized by being those in which the highest peaks in master's and/or doctorate defenses in Psychopedagogy occurred, with 15 defenses for each of these years (Table 3). If we consider the published works in relation to their type, academic master's works predominate as those with the highest number of defenses when compared to professional master's and doctoral studies (Table 3). Just for clarification, if we add up all the works defended from 1989 to 2022 in relation to their type, we have that 212 correspond to academic master's works, 16 to professional master's and 49 to doctoral degrees.

When analyzing the works defended over the last 33 years (1989 to 2022) regarding the area of knowledge, it is clear that the area of Education predominates in 29 years, with the exceptions being the 1990s, where only the defense of a the only work that was in the area of Nursing, and the years 2008, 2010 and 2012 where the largest number of works were linked to the area of knowledge of Psychology, with 6, 5 and 6 works defended, respectively (Table 3).

Regarding the availability of works for download in the CAPES Catalog of Theses and Dissertations, from 1989 to 2012 (23 years) no work is available for viewing by internet users, with the first ones only occurring in 2013. releases for downloads of dissertations and theses

financed by CAPES (Table 3), that is, only works defended in the last 9 years are available on the platform.

Table 3 - List of works in the area of Psychopedagogy cataloged on the CAPES Theses and Dissertations Catalog website, regarding their type, area of knowledge and availability for download for the period from 1989 to 2022

YEAR	NUMBER OF WORKS PUBLISHED	TYPE*			KNOWLEDGE AREA	AVAILABLE FOR DOWNLOAD
		Master's degree	Professional Master's	Doctorate degree		
1989	3	3	0	0	Education (2) and Nursing (1)	No
nineteen ninety	1	1	0	0	Nursing (1)	No
1991	3	3	0	0	Education (3)	No
1992	two	1	0	1	Education (2)	No
1993	6	6	0	0	Education (6)	No
1994	0	0	0	0	---	---
1995	15	13	0	two	Education (12), Psychology (3)	No
1996	9	6	0	3	Education (7), Psychology (2)	No
1997	8	6	0	1	Education (7), Arts (1)	No
1998	6	4	0	1	Education (4), Physical Education (1), Psychology (1)	No
1999	10	8	0	1	Education (7), Arts (1), Psychology (2)	No
2000	9	7	0	1	Education (7), Medicine (1), Psychology (1)	No
2001	7	5	0	1	Education (4), Theology (1), Psychology (2)	No
2002	7	6	0	0	Education (2), Interdisciplinary (2), Psychology (2), Communication (1)	No
2003	15	13	1	1	Education (8), Psychology (3), Speech Therapy (1), Literature (1), Public health (1)	No
2004	8	6	0	two	Education (6), Psychology (2)	No
2005	10	9	0	1	Education (5), Interdisciplinary (2), Psychology (2), Computer science (1)	No
2006	6	5	0	1	Education (4), Interdisciplinary (1), Psychology (1)	No
2007	3	two	0	1	Education (2), Psychology (1)	No
2008	15	10	0	5	Education (4), Psychology (6), Morphology (1), Nutrition (1), Pediatrics (1)	No
2009	7	6	0	1	Education (4), Psychology (3)	No
2010	8	5	0	3	Education (1), Psychology (5), Administration (1), Linguistics (1)	No
2011	11	8	two	1	Education (6), Computer science (1), Speech therapy (1), Psychology (1), Public health (1)	No
2011	11	8	two	1	Education (6), Computer science (1), Speech therapy (1), Psychology (1), Public health (1)	No

2012	14	11	1	two	Education (5), Psychology (6), Administration (1), Arts (1), Interdisciplinary (1)	No
2013	11	7	1	3	Education (7), Engineering/Technology/Management (1), Literature (1), Psychology (1), Theology (1)	Yes
2014	13	9	0	4	Education (6), Science and Mathematics Teaching (3), Literature (1), Educational Planning (1), Psychology (1)	Yes
2015	12	9	0	3	Education (3), Psychology (2), Arts (1), Dance (1), Industrial Design (1)	In part
2016	15	11	two	two	Education (10), Psychology (3), Social and Humanities (1) and Theology (1)	In part
2017	11	8	1	two	Education (6), Psychology (2), Special Education (1), Linguistics (1) and Theology (1)	In part
2018	12	6	3	3	Education (5), Psychology (2), Arts (1), Teaching (1) and Teaching-learning (1).	In part
2019	7	two	4	1	Education (4), Teaching (2) and Administration (1)	In part
2020	10	8	0	two	Education (4), Teaching-learning (4) and Social and humanities (2)	In part
2021	8	7	1	0	Education (4) Psychology (2), Teaching-learning (1) and Public Health (1)	In part
2022	1	1	0	0	Psychology (1)	Yes

This can be explained due to the fact that although the CAPES Catalog of Theses and Dissertations website was opened in July 2022, its original version was only intended to make references and summaries of theses and dissertations defended in postgraduate programs available. - *stricto sensu* graduation in the country, as highlighted on the Catalog website itself (BRASIL, 2023c).

This pattern of information availability only changed in 2013 when the CAPES Theses and Dissertations Catalog website, considering requests from its users, created a new version of the website, starting to use Elastic Search (ES) and Java technology. The tool, which allowed searching only by author, title, institution, level and year of defense of the work, now makes search available in the fields summary, keywords, library, line of research, area of knowledge, program, among others search characters (BRASIL, 2023c).

When analyzing the content of Psychopedagogy works published in the last 5 decades, with regard to the area of knowledge of Education, we have that the two works financed by CAPES in the 1980s (1980 to 1989) were characterized by covering theoretical aspects of Psychopedagogy in relation to its application methodology, with the work of Ferreira (1989)

focused on its application in the clinical part (Clinical Psychopedagogy) and the work of Silva (1989) dedicated to school Psychopedagogy.

In the following decade, the 1990s (1990 to 1999), the themes worked on in the previous decade gained even more robustness in studies such as those by Bossa (1993), Nascimento (1993), Zilio (1993), Andreoli (1995), Dias (1995), Labatut (1995), Makishima (1995), Petty (1995), Wechsler (1995), Barreto (1996), Gimenez (1996), Noffs (1996), Argenti (1997), Becker (1998) and Matioda (1998) and are complemented by new studies that link Psychopedagogy to its application in singing and/or music (OLIVEIRA, 1991; FIGUEIREDO, 1996; GIL, 1997; PAULA, 1997; BASTOS, 1999), human sexuality (SIQUEIRA, 1991), the relationship between child and transitional object (NUNES, 1991), aspects of adolescence (CESAR, 1998), the role of errors in learning (LAJONQUIERE, 1992), learning problems/difficulties (SCOZ, 1992; COLOGNESE, 1993; MORAES, 1995; CASTRO, 1996; DIAS, 1996; MANTOVANI, 1996; RODRIGUES, 1997; SGARBOSSA, 1998; RODRIGUES, 1999; RONCHIN, 1999), emotional disorders (ZUGUEIB NETO, 1993), coexistence (HEROLD, 1993), learning/ operative construction (PEREIRA, 1995; SILVA, 1995), special educational needs (GARRIDO, 1995) and psycho-pedagogical support rooms (OLIVEIRA, 1999).

In the 2000s (2000 to 2009), works addressing Psychopedagogy continued to address various themes within this theme, such as Institutional/school Psychopedagogy (BURLAMAQUI, 2000; CONCEIÇÃO, 2003), Clinical Psychopedagogy (SIQUEIRA, 2000), Psychopedagogy and its application in singing and/or music (PIRES, 2005) learning difficulties (CARDOSO, 2000; LEONÇO, 2000; SZTERLING, 2000; COLINI, 2001; MARTINS, 2001; ZUBEN, 2003; QUEIRÓS, 2003; FURTADO, 2004; SALVARI, 2004), special educational needs (CARMO, 2022; PAULA, 2003; PERUSSO, 2003), aspects of adolescence (CARARA, 2004; GALLEGO, 2006) and psychopedagogical support rooms (LEITE, 2002) that had already been discussed in the 1990s, and there is an association between some of these themes already discussed, such as Clinical and Institutional Psychopedagogy (School) with learning difficulties (ESCOTT, 2000).

New themes are addressed, such as the training of psychopedagogues (PARIZZI, 2000; LOPES, 2003; LORIJOLA, 2006), work performance of basic education teachers (GARCIA, 2005), work performance of university teachers (INOCENTE, 2000; MARQUES, 2003), the relationship between Psychopedagogy and faith (LOMÔNICO, 2001), school exclusion (SCHERVENSKI, 2001), Psychopedagogy and learning in the Third Age (OLIVEIRA, 2004),

academic productions on Psychopedagogy in Brazil (RAMOS, 2005; FONTES, 2005) and psychopedagogical monitoring in hospital schools (SOUSA, 2005).

With the arrival of the 2010s (2010 to 2019), the themes already covered in previous decades continue to be updated through new studies that were defended throughout this new decade, including new themes associated with Psychopedagogy studied in this period. social representations and Youth and Adult Education (EJA) (PEDROSO, 2010), entrepreneurship and multiple intelligences (MATIAS, 2010), school failure (MENEZES, 2011), Medicalization (EDINGTON, 2012) and Virtual Learning Environments (CASTIGLIONE, 2011).

Finally, in the current decade (2020) in which we find ourselves, new themes worked on in association with Psychopedagogy include the use of digital technological resources in psychopedagogical intervention (KRETZER, 2021) and school learning and COVID-19 (STEIN, 2022).

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Through the analysis of works financed by CAPES with the theme of Psychopedagogy, a series of information can be verified about the historical evolution of this theme in the Brazilian national scenario.

The first published works date back to 1989, addressing a priori issues such as Institutional/School Psychopedagogy and Clinical Psychopedagogy. As the years progressed, new themes were added to these, such as learning difficulties, musicalization, students with special educational needs, teacher training and the most recent theme, which was the question of the relationship between learning and the COVID-19 pandemic. .

The predominant type of works defended were academic master's dissertations, 212 in total, followed by doctoral theses (49) and professional master's dissertations (16). As for the main area of knowledge in which Psychopedagogy was studied, the area of Education predominated in 29, of the total 33 years of studies on the topic.

In this way, the historical evolution of work financed by CAPES in strictu-sensu postgraduate courses in Brazil is described, whose theme addresses the theme of Psychopedagogy as being quite variable over the years, with no continuous pattern throughout these 33 years of history. The academic master's courses were those that benefited most from CAPES scholarships, however the studies financed at the doctoral level do not even reach 50% of the studies carried out in the master's degree, which shows that such studies do not tend to have continuation/splitting or new strands of studies as the years progress.

REFERENCES

- ANDREOLI, F. **When fairies, princesses, heroes & company invade the classroom: story of a case** . 1995. 179f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Universidade Paulista, São Paulo.
- ARGENTI, PW **Psychopedagogy in a critical dimension** : a possibility of intervention in Basic Education. 1997. 160f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – University of Vale do Rio dos Sinos, São Leopoldo.
- BARRETO, M. de LM **Social integration and cognitive development** : a study with children in group games and free activities in the “Playground”. 1996. 269f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – State University of Campinas, Campinas.
- BASTOS, MBB **The educator and the process of musicalization through acoustic and electronic keyboards** . 1999. 116f. Dissertation (Master's in Music) – Brazilian Conservatory of Music, Rio de Janeiro.
- BECKER, MLR **Genetic epistemology and practice of psychopedagogy at school** : diffusion of theory and the purges of reason. 1998, 189f. Thesis (Doctorate in Education) – Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre.
- BOSSA, NAD **Psychopedagogy in Brazil** : contributions from practice. Dissertation (Master's in Education – Educational Psychology). 1993. 155f. Pontifical Catholic University of São Paulo, São Paulo.
- BOSSA, NA **Psychopedagogy in Brazil** : contributions from practice. Porto Alegre: Artmed, 2016.
- BRAZIL. History and Evolution. Catalog of Theses and Dissertations. 2023c. Available at: <https://catalogodeteses.capes.gov.br/catalogo-teses/#!/info> . Accessed on: 26 Oct. 2022.
- BRAZIL. History and Mission. **Capes** . 2023a Available at: <https://www.gov.br/capes/pt-br/acao-a-informacao/institucional/historia-e-missao> . Accessed on: 20 Jan. 2023.
- BRAZIL. Courses evaluated and recognized. Sucupira Platform. 2023b. Available at: <https://sucupira.capes.gov.br/sucupira/public/consultas/coleta/programa/quantitativos/quantitativoRegiao.jsf> . Accessed on: 07 Apr. 2023.
- BURLAMAQUI, FRR **Psychopedagogy at school** : a “new look” for old issues in the relationship between Psychology and Education? 2000. 74f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Federal University of Mato Grosso do Sul Foundation, Campo Grande.
- CARARA, MCQ **Influences of Art Education on the Self-Esteem and Self-Image of Adolescents in Psychopedagogical Care** . 2004. 260f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Pontifical Catholic University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre.
- CARDOSO, M. da S. **The integration/inclusion of students with special educational needs** : psychopedagogical implications. 2000. 294f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Pontifical Catholic University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre.

CARMO, SM do. **The teaching-learning process of learners with learning disorders** : the discovery of “looking” at the self and the other. 2022. 173f. Dissertation (Master’s in Developmental Disorders) – Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie, São Paulo.

CASTIGLIONE, RGM **Virtual learning environments in the recovery of students in military high schools** . 2011. 176f. Dissertation (Master’s in Education) – Estácio de Sá University, Rio de Janeiro.

CASTRO, EF de. **An investigation into the cognitive structure and learning in people with visual impairment** – low vision. 1996. 96f. Dissertation (Master’s in Education) – State University of Campinas, Campinas.

CESAR, MR de A. **The investigation of “adolescence” in psychopedagogical discourse** . 1998. 140f. Dissertation (Master’s in Education) – State University of Campinas, Campinas.

COLINI, AMC **Piagetian study of psychopedagogical care for a child with learning difficulties** . 2001. 75f. Dissertation (Master’s in Psychology) – São Marcos University, São Paulo.

COLOGNESIS, IN G . **Social production of learning difficulties** : Why is this a dimension not considered from the perspective of family and school groups? 1993. 186f. Dissertation (Master’s in Education) – Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre.

CONCEAÇÃO, ICL **Child conception and teaching performance in Early Childhood Education** : contributions to Institutional Psychopedagogy. 2003. 166f. Dissertation (Master’s in Psychology) – University of Fortaleza, Fortaleza.

DIAS, AC **Creative workshop and psychopedagogy** . 1995. 160f. Thesis (Doctorate in School Psychology and Human Development) – University of São Paulo, São Paulo.

EDINGTON, VLT **The medicalization of childhood** : a psychoanalytic reading. 2012. 100f. Dissertation (Master’s in Psychology) – Federal University of Bahia, Salvador.

ESCOTT, CM **Bringing together psychopedagogical theory and practice** – interfaces between clinical and institutional psychopedagogy: a look and a listen in the preventive action of learning difficulties. 2000. 123f. Dissertation (Master’s in Education) – Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre.

FERREIRA, VGN **Psychopedagogical clinic** – bases for a methodology. 1989. 176f. Dissertation (Master’s in Education) – Fluminense Federal University, Niterói.

FIGUEIREDO, EL **Evolution of creative thought in a musical situation** . 1996, 245f. Thesis (Doctorate in Education) – State University of Campinas, Campinas.

FONTES, MA **Conceptions of Psychopedagogy in Brazil** : reflections from the Critical Theory of Society. 2005. 225f. Dissertation (Master’s in School Psychology and Human Development) – University of São Paulo, São Paulo.

FURTADO, VQ **Children with difficulty in writing and special structuring** : a psychopedagogical re-education. 2004. 170f. Thesis (Doctorate in Education) – State University of Campinas, Campinas.

GALLEGO, AB **Adolescence and morality** : the teacher who makes the difference. 2006.180f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre.

GARCIA, ECAV **Educator training in elementary school I** : the possibility of understanding the student. 2005. 158f. Dissertation (Master's in Education, Administration and Communication) – Universidade São Marcos, São Paulo.

GARRIDO, ME **The evolution of possibilities in deaf children** . 1995. 146f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – State University of Campinas, Campinas.

, B.D. **Popular music lyrics** : vocabularies, conceptual fields and lexico-semantic fields as language instruments. 1997. 199f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – University of São Paulo, São Paulo.

GIMENEZ, BP **The game of rules in the games of life** . 1996. 198f. Dissertation (Master's Degree in Health Psychology) – Methodist University of São Paulo, São Bernardo do Campo.

GUARALD, IP; BAGETTI, T. Syntactic and phonological processing of children with learning difficulties. **Communication disorders** , v. 33, no. 4, p. 712-728, 2021. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.23925/2176-2724.2021v33i4p712-728> . Accessed on: February 12, 2023.

HEROLD, U. **The common territory? The private space, and being with others in the institution** . 1993. 116f. Dissertation (Master's in Education – Educational Psychology) – Pontifical Catholic University of São Paulo, São Paulo.

INOCENTE, NJ **Depressive states and work situations of university professors** . 2000. 273f. Dissertation (Master's in Medical Sciences) – State University of Campinas, Campinas.

KRETZER, EC **The use of digital technological resources in psychopedagogical intervention to improve reading fluency with basic education students from the perspective of inclusive educational processes** . 2021. 193f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Santa Catarina, Balneário Camboriú.

LABATUT, PEM **Psychopedagogy at the university** : possibilities for reflection and action - proposal for institutionalization. 1995. 90f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Pontifical Catholic University of Paraná, Curitiba.

LAJONQUIERE, L. de. **From Piaget to Freud** : Notes to rethink errors in learning. (Psycho) Pedagogy between knowledge and knowledge. 1992. 313 f. Thesis (Doctorate in Education) – State University of Campinas, Campinas.

LEITE, SRR de Sá. **The psychopedagogical workshop in the everyday classroom** : an alternative to improve learning and inclusion conditions for children with special educational

needs. 2022. 111f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Pontifical Catholic University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre.

LEONÇO, VC de. **The adolescent student in the intermediate grades** : addressing not learning in the psychopedagogical context. 2000. 250f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre.

LOMÔNICO, CF **Psychopedagogy and faith** : a dialogue between Jorge Visca's convergent Epistemology and James W. Fowler's stages of faith. 2001. 255f. Thesis (Doctorate in Religious Sciences) – Methodist University of São Paulo, São Bernardo do Campo.

LOPES, MI **Psychopedagogy** : an orthopedics of learning. 2003. 99f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre.

LORIJOLA, LM **The professional identity of the educational psychologist in Brazil** : a sociosemiotic analysis. 2006. 127f. Dissertation (Master's in Semiotics, Information Technologies and Education) – Braz Cubas University, Mogi das Cruzes.

MAIA, D. da S.; RICHETTI, VC Welcoming and bonding: Dialogue between Psychopedagogy and Popular Education from the perspective of inclusive education. **Written Education** , v. 13, no. 1, 2022, e41884. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.15448/2179-8435.2022.1.41884> . Accessed on: 03 Jan. 2023.

MAKISHIMA, ICMG **The game of seduction in the construction of knowledge** – a psychoanalytic view of the teacher-student relationship. 1995. 113f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Federal University of Paraná, Curitiba.

MANTOVANI, AM **Manifestations of affection in a telematic computational learning environment** : a psychopedagogical reading of children with learning difficulties. 1996. 281f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre.

MARQUES, WFS **Psychopedagogy and educational assessment** : perspectives on a Higher Education Institution. 2003. 91f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – State University of Campinas, Campinas.

MARTINS, N. de AR **Analysis of guidance work for families of children complaining of school difficulties** . 2001. 140f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – State University of Campinas, Campinas.

MATIAS, MA **Relationship between entrepreneurial characteristics and multiple intelligences** : a study with accountants from Minas Gerais. 2010. 115f. Thesis (Doctorate in Controllershship and Accounting) – University of São Paulo, São Paulo.

MATIODA, VL **Suggestions for a psychopedagogical proposal in Basic Education in Elementary Education** . 1998. 200f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Pontifical Catholic University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre.

MENEZES, MVE Psychopedagogy and school failure: the relevance of socio-contextual understanding. 2011. 66f. Report (Professional Course in Theology) – Higher School of Theology, São Leopoldo.

MORAES, HN de. **Opinions of students on a postgraduate course specializing in Psychopedagogy regarding their expectations regarding the course and the knowledge built during the course regarding learning difficulties** . 1995. 98f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Pontifical Catholic University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre.

MOURA, AA de; MARTINS, ED; MOURA, VA de; MARTINS, AP Psychopedagogy and its facilitating strategies in the learning process. **Online Magazine of Educational Policy and Management** , Araraquara, v. 23, no. 2, p. 479–493, 2019. DOI: 10.22633/rpge.v23i2.12654. Available at: <https://periodicos.fclar.unesp.br/rpge/article/view/12654> . Accessed on: 8 April. 2023.

NASCIMENTO, M. da G. **The role of professionals in psychopedagogy and the training of psychopedagogues in São Paulo from 1980 to 1990** . 1993. 175f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – University of São Paulo, São Paulo.

NOFFS, N. de A. **Institutional psychopedagogy** : the trajectory of its actors-authors. 1996. 203f. Thesis (Doctorate in Education) – University of São Paulo, São Paulo.

NUNES, VML de. S. **Relationship between the child's use of the transitional object and the facilitation of their socialization and learning process** . 1991, 129 f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Fluminense Federal University, Niterói.

OLIVEIRA, ETA **Creating and learning styles in the elderly** : a psychopedagogical proposal, 2004. 175f. Thesis (Doctorate in Psychology) – Pontifical Catholic University of Campinas, Campinas.

OLIVEIRA, NV de. **The psychological foundation of musical initiation, its actions and proposals in Sa Pereira's work, and its influence until modernity** . 1991, 126f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Fluminense Federal University, Niterói.

OLIVEIRA, V. de. **Psychopedagogical support rooms** : a possible rupture. 1999. 162f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Rio de Janeiro.

PARIZZI, SRM **Multiple identities** : the training and performance of the psychopedagogue. 2000. 106f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Pontifical Catholic University of Campinas, Campinas.

PAULA, LDB de. **Listening to the signals** . Development and interaction of deaf children enrolled in regular schools and special schools. 2003, 215f. Dissertation (Master's in Psychology) – University of Brasília, Brasília.

PAULA, WM de. **Respiratory management in singing supports singing teaching based on the psychopedagogical concepts of Carl Rogers and Physiology** . 1997. 88f. Dissertation (Master's in Music) – Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Rio de Janeiro.

PEDROSO, CC de C. **Social representations of history by EJA (Youth and adult education) students** . 2010. 80f. Dissertation (Master's in Educational Psychology) – Centro Universitário FIEO, Osasco.

PEREIRA, RCB **Cognitive conflict, formation of possibilities and operational construction** . 1995. 150f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – State University of Campinas, Campinas.

PERUSSO, DIR **Differential diagnosis between dyslexia and Learning Disorder Associated with Central Auditory Processing Disorder** : a case study in Education. 2003, 326f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Pontifical Catholic University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre.

PETTY, ALS **Essay on the pedagogical value of rule games from a constructivist perspective** . 1995. 133f. Dissertation (Master's in School Psychology and Human Development) – University of São Paulo, São Paulo.

PIRES, BL **Looking and listening in Music Education** : rethinking the pedagogical practice of piano and/or keyboard teachers from the perspective of the student's desire to learn. 2005. 208f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre.

QUEIRÓS, AL de. **Promoting student health through parental involvement in learning difficulties** . 2003. 94f. Dissertation (Master's in Health Education) – University of Fortaleza, Fortaleza.

RAMOS, AMP **Academic production in Psychopedagogy in Brazil** . 2005. 163f. Dissertation (Master's in Education, Administration and Communication) – Universidade São Marcos, São Paulo.

RIBEIRO, RJ What the Capes assessment is for. **Capes** . 2017. Available at: https://www.gov.br/capes/pt-br/centrais-de-conteudo/Artigo_18_07_07.pdf . Accessed on: 07 Apr. 2023.

RODRIGUES, G. de M. **Adolescents with learning difficulties** : a psychopedagogical understanding. 1999. 139f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Pontifical Catholic University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre.

RODRIGUES, TCPE **Characterization of a public psychopedagogy service in responding to learning difficulties** : analysis of its results. 1997. 150f. Dissertation (Master's in Special Education – Education of the Special Individual) – Federal University of São Carlos, São Carlos.

RONCHIN, SMR Psychopedagogy in the hospital environment: a study of children with learning difficulties. 1999. 133f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – State University of Campinas, Campinas.

SALVARI, L. da FC **The relationship between family and learning problems** : what psychologists and pedagogues think; 2004. 218f. Dissertation (Master's in Clinical Psychology) – Catholic University of Pernambuco, Recife.

SCHERVENSKI, PTD **Psychopedagogy and school exclusion** : analysis through the intelligence school (WISC). 2001. 143f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) -Federal University of Uberlândia, Uberlândia.

SCOZ, B JL **Learning problems in public schools** : a challenge for Psychopedagogy in Brazil. 1992. 350f. Dissertation (Master's in Education – Educational Psychology) – Pontifical Catholic University of São Paulo, São Paulo.

SGARBOSSA, SLZ **Psychopedagogical care and learning difficulties** . 1998. 142f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Pontifical Catholic University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre.

SILVA, FHSD **Analysis of the interference of two procedures in operative learning** . 1995. 122f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – State University of Campinas, Campinas.

SIMOES, N. **From professional metalanguage to the development of scientific technical vocabulary in the area of Nursing** . 1989. 948f. Thesis (Doctorate in Nursing) – University of São Paulo, São Paulo.

SIQUEIRA, LD de. **Homework monitoring** : a clinical intervention. 2000. 150f. Dissertation (Master's in Psychology) – Pontifical Catholic University of Campinas, Campinas.

SIQUEIRA, MLN **Educator attitudes towards contemporary themes of human sexuality** . 1991. 107f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Federal University of Amazonas, Manaus.

SOUSA, FM de. **The hospital school** : a study on school psychopedagogical support with children hospitalized for a long time. 2005. 163f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Fundação UNiversidade Federal do Piauí, Teresina.

STEIN, MEK **School learning and pandemic** : the perspective of Psychopedagogy. Dissertation (Academic Master's Degree in Psychology) – Postgraduate in Psychology - FEEVALE University, Novo Hamburgo, 2022. Available at: https://sucupira.capes.gov.br/sucupira/public/consultas/coleta/trabalhoConclusao/viewtrabalhoConclusao.jsf?popup=true&id_trabalho=11723866 . Accessed on: January 11, 2023.

SZTERLING, S. **Dialogue between psychoanalysis and psychopedagogy** : on the (im)possibility of learning. 2000. 1f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – University of São Paulo, São Paulo.

WECHSLER, MPF **Psychodrama and constructivism as a psychopedagogy** : Studies with children and adolescents. 1995, 210f. Thesis (Doctorate in School Psychology and Human Development) – University of São Paulo, São Paulo.

ZILIO, MP **Psychopedagogy** : a professional profile in conflict. 1993. 244f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Pontifical Catholic University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre.

ZUBEN, RBV **The dialectical construction in the Traverse rules game, in students complaining of school difficulties** . 2003. 210f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – State University of Campinas, Campinas.

ZUGUEIB NETO, J. **Psychopedagogical strategies in assisting young people with severe emotional disorders** . 1993. 91f. Dissertation (Master's in Education) – Federal University of Paraná.